

Talent Management: Concept, Implementation, and Indicators of Success

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of talent management, from its basic concepts to implementation in organizations, and why measuring success in talent management is important for achieving strategic goals. This paper can also provide guidance for HR practitioners and organizational leaders who wish to improve their talent management practices. This paper uses a qualitative method by looking for findings or results from papers related to the topic through international and reputable journal literature, as well as other media to obtain evidence related to this paper. This paper fully supports, accepts, and is part of the contribution in the talent management variable, although there are contradictory research results from one of the study results, but still the results of this research state that talent management in all fields and organizations has been carried out, implemented and indicators. Existing success indicators have also been used. Recommendations for other researchers in producing results papers on the same variables or with other variables contained in this paper which are found to be a gap in future research.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of talent management is centered on the understanding that employee talents and skills are valuable assets that can provide a competitive advantage and make a positive contribution to achieving business goals. The importance of this concept lies in the recognition that to achieve long-term success, organizations must proactively seek out individuals who have the potential to contribute to growth and innovation. The concept of talent management involves the employee life cycle, which includes talent procurement, employee development, performance management and succession planning.

First, talent procurement involves the process of selecting and recruiting potential individuals who suit the needs of the organization. Then, employee development becomes the focus, by providing training, coaching and experience that supports employee growth and development. Performance management means evaluating and providing feedback on employee performance to help them achieve expected results. Furthermore, succession planning is an important part of the talent management concept. This means identifying and preparing employees who can fill key roles in the organization when needed, such as managerial or leadership positions.

The Talent Management concept applies strategies to manage, develop and utilize employee talents. It involves talent procurement, employee development, performance management, and succession planning to achieve organizational goals. The concept of talent management begins with the recognition that human capital is a valuable asset for every organization. This emphasizes the need to identify high-potential individuals in the workforce and provide them with opportunities to grow and develop. This includes talent acquisition, performance management, training and development, succession planning, and employee engagement. By aligning these aspects with the organization's strategic objectives, a comprehensive framework for talent management is formed. The aim is to optimize employee potential and provide competitive advantages.

Implementing effective talent management involves several key steps. First of all, organizations need to establish a clear talent management strategy that is aligned with their overall business strategy. This strategy should define the competencies and skills required for current and future success, and should cover all levels of the organization. It also involves creating a culture that supports talent development and encourages a continuous learning environment. This is often facilitated through mentorship programs, career path planning, and training initiatives. Measuring the success of talent management initiatives is important to ensure that the concepts are implemented effectively. Key performance indicators (KPIs) can help organizations evaluate their talent management strategies. Some common indicators of success include employee engagement and retention, effectiveness of succession planning, performance improvements, skills development, time needed to fill vacancies, progress in diversity and inclusion, and cost efficiency.

Talent management has a close relationship between concept (understanding of talent management) and implementation (real actions in the organization). Concepts guide practices and policies, while implementation is the execution of practices based on concepts. Both must be aligned with business strategy, measured, evaluated and updated on an ongoing basis. Concept and implementation come together to achieve talent management goals in organizations. Success Indicators in Talent Management refer to the parameters or guidelines used to measure the achievement and success of talent management programs or initiatives in an organization. Success indicators in the context of talent management typically include a number of metrics and parameters that help organizations assess the extent to which talent management practices have achieved stated strategic objectives. Some common indicators of success in talent management include employee engagement, retention rates, improved individual and team performance, effectiveness of succession planning, skills development, and cost efficiencies in recruiting and training.

The importance of success indicators in talent management is to ensure that these initiatives provide real added value to the organization. They help organizations measure the impact, effectiveness and return on investment of the talent management programs they run. Over time, organizations can use data from these success indicators to identify areas that need improvement and improvements in talent management. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of talent management, from its basic concepts to implementation in organizations, and why measuring success in talent management is important for achieving strategic goals. This paper can also provide guidance for HR practitioners and organizational leaders who wish to improve their talent management practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Talent Management

According to a study from (Ansar & Baloch, 2018) talent management includes the process of attracting, identifying, grooming, and retaining talented individuals who can make valuable contributions to organizational achievements. It involves establishing a culture of talent management, standardizing talent management systems, and implementing plans to attract, develop, and retain competent individuals. achievement, among other benefits. Successful talent management depends on transparent procedures, full involvement of all sectors within the institution, and the use of diverse techniques such as assessment centers, talent groups, and development programs (D. Zhulamanova et al., 2022) .

Talent management provides benefits to both organizations and employees. Organizations experience increased productivity and skills, increased linkage between individual efforts and business goals, commitment from valued employees, lower turnover rates, stronger talent pools, and increased linkage of job roles to employee skills. Employees, in turn, benefit in the form of increased motivation and commitment, career development

opportunities, deeper understanding of and contribution to company goals, as well as ongoing motivation and job satisfaction (Agarwal, 2017) .

Implementation Talent Management

To implement talent management, an incentive mechanism for professional development is needed that focuses on attracting, developing and retaining talented individuals (Salteh et al., 2021) , also According to (Karimi & Ntarangwi, 2019) implementing talent management involves the formation of a talent management culture, simplification talent management processes, and implementing strategies to attract, develop, and retain talented individuals. Successful talent management depends on transparent processes, involvement of all elements within the institution, and the use of a variety of methods such as assessment centers, talent groups, and development programs.

Executing talent management necessitates the establishment of a motivational system for professional development with the objectives of drawing, nurturing, and preserving skilled individuals. Organizations must adhere to a transparent talent acquisition and management strategy, with a primary focus on acquiring talented employees, ensuring the retention of their top talents within the organization (Daruka, 2022) , According to (Kamadajaja et al., 2013) Implementing talent management can result in a range of advantages, including enhanced productivity, capabilities, and the dedication of highly valued employees, among other positive outcomes.

Indicators of Success Talent Management

Indicators of success in talent management may differ based on the organization and its particular circumstances. Nonetheless, some typical markers of success in talent management encompass increased productivity, capabilities, and the commitment of esteemed employees, Success indicators could encompass elevated performance metrics, such as increased success in commercialization within biotechnology start up companies. (Mansour, 2015; Yadav & Dyaram, 2015) . Furthermore, an investigation into HR management education in Ukraine discovered that the efficacy of HR managers is primarily influenced by their interactions with coworkers and interactions, along with the social recognition of leadership of their work by their superiors, as opposed to relying on market success indicators for the company (Pylat, 2017) .

Hence, it is crucial for organizations to pinpoint the unique markers of success in talent management and consistently assess their talent management approaches to guarantee they are achieving their objectives (Ma et al., 2020) .

METHODOLOGY

This paper uses a qualitative method by looking for findings or results from papers related to the topic through international and reputable journal literature, as well as other media to obtain evidence related to this paper. Then the researcher looks at a finding and adapts it to the purpose of this paper, then an assumption is made in the discussion and a conclusion is made.

RESEARCH RESULT

The results of this paper look at the results of the findings of various literary papers found related to the topic in this paper starting from a study belonging to (Ansar & Baloch, 2018) which traces the evolution of the meaning of the term talent through various historical periods, starting from its use in biblical times to describe the number of significant money to contemporary interpretations as cognitive abilities. A philological perspective is also used to identify the linguistic origins of various interpretations of "Talent" in various languages, and alternative terms used as synonyms of talent are also explored, with the findings of this paper being the importance of developing a uniform definition for talent and talent management in order to facilitating shared understanding, both in academic research and practical applications in the corporate sector.

According to a study from (Caya et al., 2022) stating the development of talent management for the preparation of future leaders, talent management reflects a paradigm shift in human resource management, with two main definitions, namely exclusive and inclusive. Both definitions aim to increase the organization's chances of achieving its goals, in contrast to the study from (Sackey, 2022) which states that talent management has been recognized by organizations, there is still uncertainty about what is actually meant by talent management and how it can be implemented optimally, there is no agreement on definition and theoretical basis of management, efforts are theoretical in nature and do not provide clear views and guidance for organizations in the domain of talent management.

A study from (Angosto-fernández et al., 2022) states that the concept of talent management requires renewed attention because the environment may not return to normal conditions before the pandemic, followed by an opinion from (DB Zhulamanova et al., 2022) stating that the importance of introducing management talent in all sectors of the economy and especially in the field of education. Considering this trend changes according to the demands of time. Several findings from existing literature state that management talent is present in research results.

Next, discussing the implementation of talent management starting from a study from (Karimi & Ntarangwi, 2019) stating that human resource planning and talent management shows that the human resources department maintains a database of all employees in the Human Resources Information System (HRIS) to facilitate proper HR planning. time. Pearson correlation analysis shows the positive and significant influence of human resource planning on talent management. The following opinion from the study (Kravariti & Johnston, 2020) states in the results of its paper that it contributes to this field by: (1) providing a definition of talent and talent management in the context of the public sector; (2) evaluate the feasibility of implementing talent management for public organizations by assessing the internal and external factors that influence its implementation; and (3) critically evaluate the possibility of implementing talent management principles in the public sector.

A study from (Whysall et al., 2019) states the need to explore new and more efficient talent development methods. In particular, middle managers are now recognized as an important but often overlooked talent in the context of unprecedented transformation, especially because of their key role in change management. Implementing an efficient talent management process is very important to improve organizational performance in Indonesia in facing the challenges of Industry 4.0. These findings provide a valuable contribution to existing literature by providing insight into the role of talent management in accommodating and improving organizational performance in Indonesia (Wolor et al., 2020) .

Another study states that educational institutions need to organize training programs for employees that will help them acquire job-related competencies. The benefits of implemented talent management effectively increase the retention ratio (Shrivastava, 2022) . Implementation in talent management of various literature findings with various organizations that have been used and applied.

The indicators of success in the explanation found and described in this paper with a study from (Tafti et al., 2017) state that talent management is classified into four categories, namely structural barriers and challenges, environmental barriers and challenges, behavioral barriers and challenges, and finally barriers. and managerial challenges, apart from that, the talent management success factors framework is categorized into three main parts, namely structural success factors, environmental success factors, and finally managerial success factors. There is a positive influence in implementing talent management strategies on project success, where the framework of obstacles and challenges in talent management is classified into four categories, namely structural obstacles and challenges, environmental obstacles and challenges, behavioral obstacles and challenges, and finally managerial obstacles and challenges. In addition, the talent management success factors framework is categorized into three main parts, namely structural success factors, environmental success factors, and finally managerial success factors.

Four groups of work-life balance (WLB) indicators based on employees' direct experience in the front office were identified and presented. Human resources revealed that hotels consider existing work-life balance practices as resource management practices. key human resources with an inclusive talent management approach, with a talent management approach there are differences in employee expectations in the front office and work life balance practices implemented by hotels (Budhiraja et al., 2022)

DISCUSSION

In the description of dozens of papers obtained to support this paper, this paper is represented directly or in some contradictory ways, which is contrary to the study (Sackey, 2022) where talent management has been recognized by organizations, there is still a lack of clarity about what it really is. what is meant by talent management and how its implementation can be carried out optimally. Apart from that, the variables from this paper are also related to

several other variables from existing papers in the literature, such as human resource information systems, organizational performance, and work life balance.

The objects of this research findings are educational institutions, public organizations and others. So this paper is fully fulfilled from supporting references in the results.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper fully supports, accepts, and is part of the contribution in the talent management variable, although there are contradictory research results from one of the study results, but still the results of this research state that talent management in all fields and organizations has been carried out, implemented and indicators -Existing success indicators have also been used.

Recommendations for other researchers in producing results papers on the same variables or with other variables contained in this paper which are found to be a gap in future research.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This paper, as stated above, is part of the contribution to results in the field of qualitative talent management.

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This paper can serve as a reference and contribution to the institution where the researcher is based, and to the community, as well as profit and non-profit organizations.

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